

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ASONG****FIRST NAME: ABELT LEKE****PROGRAM CODE: ACA-401D****COURSE CODE: DME****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 11%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE DME ACA 401

1. What are the key strategies for clearly writing a dissertation?
 - Use long, complex sentences and paragraphs to elaborate on ideas.
 - Write short sentences, avoid page-long paragraphs, and signal transition.¹**
 - Incorporate elaborate formulations, esoteric words, and neologisms.
 - None of the above.
2. Outline the steps a beginning researcher can take to find a topic of interest.
 - Start with what interests you; Make your topic manageable; Question your topic; Evaluate your questions.²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 13.

² Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 24–28.

- Consult with a senior researcher or advisor to get a list of topics.
 - Read the latest research papers in leading journals.
 - Attend workshops and seminars to find trending topics.
3. Which of the following statements best explains the concept that “you can’t judge a source until you read it, but there are signs of its reliability?”
- You should trust any source published in a book or journal.
 - It is possible to determine the reliability of a source solely based on its title and author.
 - Before entirely judging a source, consider indicators of its reliability, such as the publisher’s reputation, whether it has been peer-reviewed, the author’s credentials, the sponsorship of online sources, and the currency of the information.³**
 - The reliability of a source can only be assessed after reading it entirely.
4. What systematic approach is suggested before beginning the dissertation concept paper?
- Focusing solely on the master’s thesis.
 - Relying on peer feedback.
 - Examining various aspects of the topic through coursework, literature reviews, and research proposals.⁴**
 - Starting with a new topic immediately.

³ Turabian et al., 42.

⁴ James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 18.

5. What is the importance of methodology in a research study?
- It determines the techniques, procedures, or tools used to generate and analyze data.
 - It dictates how the researcher thinks about the study, makes decisions, and engages with participants and data.
 - It involves planning and articulating the research design and selecting data collection methods that align with the research approach and methodology.
 - All of the above.**⁵
6. What are the most commonly used types of qualitative data collection methods in research?
- The problem statement.
 - Quantitative method.
 - Interviews, observations, focus groups, and document review.**⁶
 - All of the above.
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7. What is the key objective of the literature review in research?
- To provide a simplistic summative description of the contents of articles and books.
 - To summarize isolated previous studies.

⁵ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 256.

⁶ Bloomberg and Volpe, 56–57.

- To give a clear and balanced picture of current leading concepts, theories, and data relevant to the topic or subject of study.⁷**
- To focus solely on electronic media.
8. Which of the following statements accurately describes the difference between primary and secondary sources?
- Primary sources contain the original work of researchers and authors, providing firsthand information, while secondary sources describe, summarize, or discuss information presented initially in primary sources.⁸**
- Primary sources include abstracts, indexes, and encyclopedias, while secondary sources include scholarly research articles and interviews.
- Primary sources are always more reliable than secondary sources.
- Secondary sources provide firsthand accounts of specific topics, while primary sources combine knowledge from many secondary sources.
9. According to the European Commission English Style Guide, which guidelines should be followed regarding language usage?
- American English should be preferred over British English.
- Colloquial British English should be used extensively.
- British English should be preferred, and Americanisms should be avoided if they are not understandable to speakers of British English.⁹**

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 352.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 365.

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Eighth edition (European Commission, 2021), 7.

- Non-native speakers should be the primary focus, and very colloquial British English should be used to cater to them.

10. Which of the following correctly matches the salutation and closing of a letter according to the European Commission guidelines provided?

- A letter starting with 'Dear Sir/Madam' should finish with 'Yours sincerely.'
- A letter with 'Dear' and the recipient's name should finish with 'Yours faithfully.'
- A letter addressed to the president of an organization should start with 'Dear President' and not 'Dear [Name]'.¹⁰**
- In private correspondence, it is preferable to address the addressee by their title rather than by their name.

¹⁰ European Commission, 121.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024.
- European Commission. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. Eighth edition. European Commission, 2021.
- Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.
- Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Sta. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.